

Brand Guidelines

Version 1.0

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Table of contents

Brand concept

01 The Concept

- 1.1 The atmosphere
- 1.2 Research

The system

02 Logo

- 2.1 Logo
- 2.2 Logo versions
- 2.3 Logo safe-zone
- 2.4 Logo placement
- 2.5 Logo lock-ups
- 2.6 Slogan lock-ups
- 2.7 Social Media profile icons

03 Colours

- 3.1 Atmosphere gradients
- 3.2 Primary colours
- 3.3 Secondary colours

04 Typography

- 4.1 Brand fonts
- 4.2 Font hierarchy

05 Layout system

- 5.1 Grid

Applications

06 Templates

- 6.1 Event materials
- 6.2 Social media
- 6.3 Business card

Welcome to the ACTRIS brand guide. This document maps out the core parts we need to know about our brand, and provides a practical guide to any executional needs.

It is a creative springboard inspiring us to live the ACTRIS brand throughout all our outputs.

Concept

Logo

Typography

Aa 0 1

Colours

01 The Concept

02 Logo

03 Colours

04 Typography

05 Layout system

06 Templates

The Concept

The atmosphere

Everything we work with ties back to the atmosphere – measuring types of aerosols, calculating cloud coverage, and tracing the origins of gases in the atmosphere.

Even if our work centres around the atmosphere, it is also varied. One team may be working with a current discovery regarding trace gases and another with a yearly report of ACTRIS facilities.

To tackle this variety of research topics, our visual identity uses abstract imagery, loosely portraying the colors of the sky. This abstraction allows us to communicate any topic, regardless of the theme. It allows for a lot of imagination on the viewers part.

With its millions of colours, the sky inspires our brand. We have several predefined gradients at our disposal that allow us to illustrate different times of the day and layers of the atmosphere.

Additionally, we show that atmospheric research can be quite beautiful as well.

Research

When more concrete conclusions have to be made we can use the atmospheric gradients as backdrops for more precise content.

Lines are an important element that brings a sense of precision to our visual look. Lines can be blended into the atmosphere to give the appeal of them beaming up into the atmosphere.

Dots represent both the aerosols, clouds, and trace gases that exist in the atmosphere, and when placed in a grid-like formation, they start to look like data points. These data points can be used as abstract illustrations, or then they can be used to illustrate precise data as part of an infographic.

01 The Concept

02 Logo

03 Colours

04 Typography

05 Layout system

06 Templates

The Logo

Primary logo

The primary focus is on the word "ACTRIS" as a wholesome Research Infrastructure, representing a single community. Above the text, there is an arc that gradually shifts from light turquoise to dark blue, symbolising the atmosphere and its layers. This arc subtly conveys ACTRIS scientific focus on the atmosphere without overwhelming it with detail or highlighting any other components.

The logo incorporates a vertical line rising from the letter "I", thus placing the focus on the word "infrastructure". Also, the beam represents ACTRIS exploration of the atmosphere, hence connecting well with ACTRIS slogan "Exploring the Atmosphere" and its commitment to researching atmospheric processes.

Logo versions

The gradient arc version of the ACTRIS logo is the primary version and should be used whenever feasible, as it best represents the brand's dynamic and refined appeal.

To ensure optimal visibility and contrast:

- Use the gradient logo on backgrounds that allow it to stand out clearly, avoiding situations where it blends or becomes difficult to read.
- If the background colour or pattern is challenging and does not provide sufficient contrast for the gradient logo, opt for the white or black versions of the logo as alternatives.
- Always prioritise clarity and legibility when choosing which logo version to apply.

Logo safe-zone

The logo safe-zone ensures that logo stays visually decluttered. The width of the safe-zone is determined using the distance between the base of the logo and the intersection of the arc and the beam.

Do not place any other elements inside the area of the logo safe-zone.

Logo placement

According to the brand guidelines, the logo can be placed in corners, centred along an edge or in the middle of layouts. We favour placing the logo in areas that avoid visual cluttering, e.g. upper right corner of presentations.

Logo lock-ups

The logo is combined with lock-ups for ACTRIS Central Facilities, ACTRIS Countries, and ACTRIS ERIC, available in three colour versions: gradient, off-white, and space black.

For ACTRIS Topical Centres-specific lock-ups, the logo features versions that incorporate abbreviated Topical Centre names, maintaining consistency with the ACTRIS branding.

Germany

Centre for Cloud
Remote Sensing

CREGARS

European
Research
Infrastructure
Consortium

Making logo lock-ups

Wordmarks are added using our brand font. A divider is set between the logo and the wordmark, keeping the logo safezone uncluttered.

The logo, the divider, and the wordmark are aligned to the bottom, along the baseline of the logotype.

The spaces between the logo and the divider and the divider and the wordmark are the same and equal to the space between the bottom of the logo and the middle of the intersection of the arc and the beam.

Logos with short wordmarks:

- The font size of the wordmark is the same as the font size of the logo
- The divider has the same height as the wordmark

Logos with long titles (several lines):

- The height of the whole wordmark is adjusted to the size of the green square
- The divider has the same height as the wordmark and the green square

The divider line should always be the same height as the wordmark.

Slogan lock-up

Exploring the
Atmosphere

Our brand uses two ways of combining our slogan with the logo: one horizontal and one centred.

The horizontal version is used along the edges or in the left aligned layouts. The centred lock-up is used in centred layouts, such as ending slides in presentations.

Logos lock-ups for social media

Profile pictures on social media use a secondary, vertical variant of the country logo lock-ups.

01 The Concept

02 Logo

03 Colours

04 Typography

05 Layout system

06 Templates

Colours

Atmosphere gradients

Atmosphere gradients are the most fundamental graphic in our brand. They are used, as our brand concept describes, to illustrate our work abstractly. This allows us to communicate any topic without having a graphic being too specific to any area.

Atmosphere gradients are always constructed by using three of our brand colours, either from our primary or our secondary colour palette.

Atmosphere gradients

These are our predefined atmosphere gradients. The gradients are designed to mimic different times of the day and different heights in the atmosphere.

The numbers indicate which colour has been used from our brand colour palette. See the brand colour palettes for the exact colour values.

The last gradient in our primary palette that captures the essence of ACTRIS identity, closely resembling the already familiar ACTRIS colours.

Primary colours

The main colours of our brand are space black and off-white. These colours are mainly used in the documents but can also be complemented with different gradients. Using the primary colours, we keep our brand visually clean and simple to use.

When variation is needed, off-white can be altered with white light and space black can be changed to off-black.

White Light 1

HEX	FFFFFF
RGB	255 255 255
CMYK	0 0 0 0

Space Black 3

HEX	010025
RGB	1 0 37
CMYK	100 91 47 78

Off-White 2

HEX	F1F1F3
RGB	241 241 243
CMYK	7 5 4 0

Off-Black 4

HEX	29293D
RGB	41 41 61
CMYK	87 78 46 55

Secondary colours

The secondary color palettes are designed to complement the primary colors, offering flexibility and vibrancy when additional emphasis is needed.

These should be used strategically to enhance elements such as highlights, key messages, or data points and infographics. They work well for subtle backgrounds, transitions, and graphical elements like charts and icons, adding depth and dimension without overpowering the content and ensuring readability and a professional aesthetic. When used thoughtfully, they bring a modern and dynamic touch to ACTRIS's communication materials.

Day time		Sun Light	
Day A 5		Sun 8	
HEX	CCE1F2	HEX	FCEAB8
RGB	204 225 242	RGB	252 234 184
CMYK	24 5 2 0	CMYK	2 7 35 0
Day B 6		Day C 7	
HEX	9EC9EC	HEX	629EE4
RGB	158 201 236	RGB	98 158 228
CMYK	42 11 0 0	CMYK	62 30 0 0
Dusk			
Dusk A 9		Dusk B 10	
HEX	FDC59F	HEX	F1B3C1
RGB	253 197 159	RGB	241 179 193
CMYK	0 29 40 0	CMYK	2 39 13 0
Dusk C 11		Dusk D 12	
HEX	F86A71	HEX	72465E
RGB	248 106 113	RGB	114 70 94
CMYK	0 71 43 0	CMYK	53 73 38 30
Night Time		Northern Lights	
Night A 13		Northern Lights A 15	
HEX	5F54A6	HEX	8CDECD
RGB	95 84 166	RGB	140 222 205
CMYK	74 72 0 0	CMYK	47 0 28 0
Night B 14		Northern Lights B 16	
HEX	2C347F	HEX	2398AA
RGB	44 52 127	RGB	35 152 170
CMYK	99 89 15 3	CMYK	76 20 30 3

01 The Concept

02 Logo

03 Colours

04 Typography

05 Layout system

06 Templates

Typography

Brand fonts

Download [Open Sans from Google Fonts](#)

Our brand font is called Open Sans. It features an approachable appeal while communicating functionality and clarity. Open Sans can be used in all sizes.

We use Open Sans in all our brand communication.

00

Aerosols

Open Sans Bold

01

Clouds

Open Sans Semibold

02

Trace Gases

Open Sans Regular

03

Research

Open Sans Light

Font hierarchy

Open Sans Bold		
Size	12	px
Leading	95	%
Letterspacing	10	%

ALERT

Open Sans Bold		
Size	18	px
Leading	130	%
Letterspacing	10	%

Why ACTRIS?

Headlines

The larger the headline the lighter the font should be. Large font sizes allow us to switch to Open Sans Light while retaining a clear hierarchy between headlines and body copy. The smaller the difference between font sizes, the heavier cut should be chosen for the headline.

Body copy

In larger body copy we can choose to use Open Sans Light, but a good rule of thumb is to use Open Sans Regular in body copy.

Infographics

Open Sans features beautiful numbers. Therefore we can choose moments to use numbers in large sizes and light cuts.

Open Sans Light		
Size	80	px
Leading	100	%
Letterspacing	-3	%

Exploring the Atmosphere

Open Sans Regular		
Size	24	px
Leading	130	%
Letterspacing	0	%

The atmosphere is a highly complex system driven by countless chemical and physical processes.

Open Sans Regular		
Size	12	px
Leading	150	%
Letterspacing	2	%

ACTRIS is the fundamental European Research Infrastructure for short-lived atmospheric constituents increasing the excellence in Earth system observation and research and providing information and knowledge for developing sustainable solutions to societal needs.

Open Sans Regular		
Size	24	px
Leading	130	%
Letterspacing	0	%

1.5 degree celsius increase

01 The Concept

02 Logo

03 Colours

04 Typography

05 Layout system

06 Templates

Layout System

Grid

By leaving enough empty space, i.e. white space, a clean and minimalistic look is achieved.

Supporting innovation

A potential large market exists in Europe for improving air pollution control and monitoring, use of renewable energy, and developing cost-effective and innovative instrumentation.

ACTRIS provides an enabling environment for new opportunities of innovation and transfer of knowledge with the private sector. Far from being just a provider, companies (including SME) turn into active RI users and innovation co-developer thanks to collaborations and services accessed through the ACTRIS Catalogue of Services.

ACTRIS facilities can provide unique insights into new or existing products, help resolve technical uncertainties, and enable innovation, thus supporting pre-competitive and pre-commercial R&D. European, national and international businesses take advantage of experimental test sites and calibration centers for advancing their knowledge-based activities. ACTRIS actively promotes the conversion of research results into competitive applications, in addition to promoting new qualified ancillary industries, knowledge spillover, and industrial spin-offs through a collaborative innovation approach.

01 The Concept

02 Logo

03 Colours

04 Typography

05 Layout system

06 Templates

Templates

Event visualisations

ACTRIS is the pan-European research infrastructure producing high-quality data and information on short-lived atmospheric constituents and on the processes leading to the variability of these constituents in natural and controlled atmospheres.

The Edge of Outer Space	
Aerosols	0.0002 %
Clouds	0 %
Trace gases	0 %

Exosphere	
Aerosols	0.001 %
Clouds	0 %
Trace gases	10 %

Stratosphere	
Aerosols	0.02 %
Clouds	30 %
Trace gases	5 %

The Aerosol, Clouds and Trace Gases Research Infrastructure

We provide

We provide information on the composition and variability and of the physical, optical and chemical properties of short-lived atmospheric constituents, from the surface throughout the troposphere to the stratosphere, with the required level of precision, coherence, and integration.

We provide information and understanding of the atmospheric processes driving the formation, transformation, and removal of short-lived atmospheric constituents.

Billboard

The four-day science conference aims to bring together members of different atmospheric science communities to discuss the latest scientific breakthroughs e.g., in air quality and climate research.

ACTRIS Science Conference

Page posts

ACTRIS

9,028 followers

7h

Short-term forecast
of conditions for
photovoltaics and
wind energy

	Aerosols	0,02 %
	Clouds	30 %
	Trace gases	5 %

ACTRIS

9,028 followers

8h

Supporting innovation

Innovation portfolio

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The Innovation Portfolio displayed below showcases the distinctive innovation offer of ACTRIS to facilitate the interaction and matching with the demand for innovation coming from the private sector.

Success stories of collaboration are also highlighted to demonstrate how the provision of the ACTRIS services impacted companies in the different sectors.

Business card

actris.eu

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Getting in touch

If you are having any questions regarding the ACTRIS Visual Identity implementation process or you want us to assist you in using any of the templates, please contact our Communication Team.

We are happy to help you.

communications@actris.eu

The logo graphic consists of a white curved line that starts on the left, arches over the text, and ends on the right. A vertical white line descends from the peak of the curve, passing through the letter 'I' in the word 'ACTRIS'.

ACTRIS